

Synthesis of β -Naphthol Derivatives. Part VI. 3-Alkyl- β -naphthols, 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde and its Derivatives

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3-Methyl-, 3-ethyl-, 3-propyl- and 3-butyl- β -naphthols, the corresponding keto- β -naphthols and their methyl ethers, and some derivatives of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde, such as, anils, chalcones, and nitro compounds, have been synthesised as potential anti-infective agents.

A study of the various derivatives of β -naphthol, synthesised and evaluated by Khorana *et al.*¹⁻³, indicates that substitution in position 3 of β -naphthol nucleus may have special significance as far as their anti-infective properties are concerned. Synthesis of 3-alkyl-, 3-aldehyde- and 1-nitro-3-aldehyde- β -naphthol was therefore undertaken. Preparation of anils and chalcones of the aldehyde derivatives also was considered desirable for similar reasons. Data on keto derivatives and their ethers, obtained as intermediates in the preparation of alkyl derivatives and hydrazones of the ketonic ethers, are also reported. The anti-infective properties of all these compounds will be reported elsewhere.

Fries and Schimmelschmidt⁴ synthesised 2-methoxy-3-acetylnaphthalene by treating 2-methoxy-3-naphthoyl chloride with methylzinc iodide in toluene. Hunsberger⁵ and later Schmid and Seiler⁶ synthesised the same by treating 2-methoxy-3-naphthoyl chloride with dimethylcadmium in dry benzene. The latter method has been followed by us as the technique is simpler, more convenient, and provides higher yields. Further, the cadmium salt has a relatively low capacity for reacting with the carbonyl group. The methoxyketones were demethylated with dry pyridine hydrochloride to afford the keto-naphthols and the latter were reduced by the Haug-Minlon⁷ modification of the Wolff-Kishner procedure to yield the desired 3-alkyl- β -naphthols.

3-Aldehyde- β -naphthol has been prepared by the standard procedure of Rosenmund's reduction of 2-acetoxy-3-naphthoyl chloride^{8,11-13} with hydrogen and palladium on barium sulphate in xylene at 130-40° to provide 2-acetoxy-3-naphthaldehyde which was next hydrolysed in the cold with 2*N*-KOH. The above method being lengthy, we prepared the aldehyde more conveniently from naphthol AS by applying Sonn and Muller's⁹⁻¹⁰ modification. Incidentally, naphthol AS is produced abundantly in this country. The nitro

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3. *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1957, **48**, 603; 1958, **49**, 537.
4. *Ber.*, 1925, **58**, 2835.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 5626.
6. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1952, **35**, 1990.
7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 2487.
8. Boehm and Profft, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1931, **269**, 25.
9. *Ber.*, 1919, **52**, 1927.
10. "Organic Reactions", Vol. VIII, p. 240.

derivatives, anils, and chalkones were prepared by the usual procedures. Analytical data and other characteristics of the compounds are presented in Tables I and II.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methoxy-3-keto-naphthalenes.—2-Methoxy-3-naphthoyl chloride was prepared by methylating 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid with dimethyl sulphate in alkaline media (m.p. 132-33°) and refluxing the product with thionyl chloride⁶. The acid chloride was purified by distillation under vacuum.

The Grignard reagent, dimethylcadmium, was prepared by following Gillman's method¹⁵, using magnesium turnings (15.1 g., 0.205*M*) and alkyl halide (0.02*M*) (CH₃I, C₂H₅Br & C₃H₇Br). Following Cason's procedure¹⁶, anhydrous CdCl₂ (19 g., 0.01*M*) was added during 5 minutes to the ice-cold solution of alkylmagnesium halide in absolute ether. After stirring for 5-10 minutes, the ether was rapidly removed and thiophene-free benzene (60 ml) was added. The mixture was gently refluxed with stirring until a negative test for the Grignard was obtained (30 mins.). The benzene was removed by distillation and the cake was suspended in fresh dry benzene (60 ml).

To the dimethylcadmium suspension at 0-5° a solution of 2-methoxy-3-naphthoyl chloride (22 g., 0.1*M*) in dry benzene (100 ml) was added slowly over 30 minutes with constant stirring. After stirring further for 1 hour, the mixture was allowed to come to room temperature (30°), then slowly heated to boiling, and refluxed for 2 hours. The mixture was next cooled and carefully decomposed with ice and water. Sufficient H₂SO₄ (dil.) was added to dissolve the white precipitate. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with benzene (2×50ml). The combined benzene extract was successively washed with water, NaHCO₃ (dil.), and water and dried (Na₂SO₄). After removing benzene, the residue was distilled under vacuum (65-80%). 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones of the ketones were prepared in the usual manner.

3-Keto-β-naphthols.—The methyl ethers, obtained as above, were refluxed with pyridine hydrochloride (1:3.5 g.) for 1 hour and the mixture, while hot, poured in ice-cold, acidulated water. The product separating was filtered, washed, and crystallised (yield 60-70%).

3-Alkyl-β-naphthols.—3-Methyl-β-naphthol was prepared by reducing¹⁷ 3-hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde by the Haug-Minlon modification of the Wolff-Kishner procedure⁷.

For higher homologues, a mixture of 3-keto-β-naphthols (6 g.), diethylene glycol (35 ml), and hydrazine hydrate 95% (6 ml) was slowly heated to 100-10° and the temperature was maintained thereat for 5-10 mins. It was next cooled, mixed well with KOH (4.5 g.), and gently refluxed for 1 hour. After removing the condenser, the temperature was slowly raised to 210°, the condenser was then replaced, and the mixture gently refluxed for 3 to 4 hours. The mixture was next cooled, diluted with ice water, acidified, and extracted

11. Baker and Carruther, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 479.

12. Wahl, *Compt. rend.*, 1938, 206, 521.

13. Arnold and Sprung, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 1163.

14. Tishler *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1940, 62, 2866.

15. Gillman *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1929, 51, 1576.

16. Cason and Prout, *ibid.*, 1944, 66, 47.

TABLE I

 β -Naphthol derivatives.

Compound.	M.P. or B.P.	Cryst. form.	Cryst. shape.	Formula.	% Carbon. Found. Reqd.	% Hydrogen. Found. Reqd.	% Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.
A. 2-Methoxy-3-keto-naphthalenes.							
1. 3-Acetyl-	146/0.9 mm ⁴ ;	..	Pale yellow oil	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂	77.50	5.90	6.04
2. 3-Propionyl-	170-71°/0.7-0.8	..	"	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂	78.40	6.30	6.50
3. 3-Butyryl-	172-73°/2-3	..	"	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂	78.50	6.90	7.06
B. 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.							
Orange micro-							
4. DNP of No. 2	144-45°	EtOH	crystals	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂			14.4
" No. 3	126-27°	"	"	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂			18.6
C. β -Keto- β -naphthols.							
6. 3-Acetyl-	119.5-14°+ δ	Light petroleum	Golden leaflets	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂	77.50	5.40	5.41
7. 3-Propionyl-	101-102°	Dil. MeOH	Golden needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂	78.30	6.30	6.04
8. 3-Butyryl-	88-80°	"	"	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂	78.60	6.50	6.59
D. 3-Alkyl- β -naphthols.							
9. 3-Methyl-	161°+4	Light petroleum	Shining needles				
10. 3-Ethyl-	76-77°	Dil. EtOH	Shining platelets	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O	83.70	83.69	7.03
11. 3-Propyl-	60-61°; 140°/1.5mm	Light petroleum	"	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O	83.80	83.83	7.58
12. 3-Butyl-	80-81°; 160°/2-2.5	"	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O	83.60	83.90	8.05

TABLE II

 β -Naphthol derivatives.

Compound.	M.P.	Cryst. form.	Cryst. shape.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1. 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde	98°-99° ¹¹⁻¹³	EtOH (dil.)	Shining yellow flakes			
A. Anils of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde.						
2. Anil	158° ⁹	EtOH	Golden leaflets			
3. <i>p</i> -Chloroanil	205-206°	"	"	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ONCl	N : 5.50%	5.00%
4. <i>p</i> -Nitroanil	228-229° (d)	Benzene	Orange-yellow bangles	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	N : 9.10	9.58
5. <i>p</i> -Acetoanil	217° (d)	"	Orange-yellow leaflets	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	N : 4.70	4.84
6. <i>p</i> -Ethylcarboxy-anil	158-59°	Light petroleum	Shining yellow needles	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	N : 4.10	4.39
B. Chalcones of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde.						
7. Acetone	180-93° (d) ⁹	Dil. EtOH	Yellow needles	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂	C : 78.70 H : 6.70	79.20 6.70
8. Acetophenone	181.5-82.5° ⁹	EtOH	Yellowish needles	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂	C : 82.90 H : 5.10	83.20 5.15
9. 1-Nitro-2-hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde	186.5-86.5° (d) ⁷	"	Shining orange-red needles	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	N : 6.10	6.45
C. Anils of 1-nitro-2-hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde.						
10. Anil	184.5-85.7° (d)	Benzene and petroleum	Brown silky needles	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂	N : 9.10	9.59
11. <i>p</i> -Nitroanil	208-207° (d)	Pyridine and acetic acid	Yellow-brown needles	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	N : 6.70	6.57

with benzene. The benzene extract was washed with water and dried; the residue after removing the solvent was distilled under vacuum. Recrystallisation provided the desired product (45-50%).

2-Hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde.— PCl_5 (10 g., 0.05 *M*) was added to a suspension of naphthalen-1-ol (13 g., 0.05 *M*) in dry benzene (50 ml) at room temperature (30°). After the vigorous reaction had subsided, the mixture was shaken intermittently for 1 hour under hood and then heated at 45° for 1 hour. The solvent and POCl_3 were removed under diminished pressure, leaving a dark red, glassy imidochloride. The imidochloride was dissolved in dry benzene (60 ml) and the solution slowly added to an excess of anhydrous stannous chloride (32 g., 3.5 *M*), previously treated with dry HCl gas in ether (100 ml), at 0° under constant stirring over 1 hour. After stirring for 3 to 4 hours at 0°, the mass was left for 48 hours. The solvent was decanted from the tin complex salt which crystallised in shining orange needles; the crystalline residue was decomposed by heating with HCl (dil., under hood). The resulting mass was filtered and washed with HCl (dil.) and then with water. The aldehyde was extracted with ethanol and purified either through bisulphite or by steam distillation. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol in shining pale yellow flakes, m.p. 98-99°, yield 3.5-4 g. (40-50%). No depression in m.p. was found when admixed with an authentic sample⁸.

1-Nitro-2-hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde.—To a suspension of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde (6.8 g., 0.04 *M*) in acetic acid (50 ml) HNO_3 (3g., 0.05 *M*) in acetic acid (16 ml) was added at 5° over 30 mins. with constant stirring. After stirring for further 2 hours, the mixture was poured over ice and water. The product separating was washed with water and crystallised; yield 4.6 g. (55%).

Anils of the Aldehydes.—A mixture of the aldehyde (1 *M*) and the appropriate aromatic amine (1.1 *M*) in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 30 minutes and then cooled. The separated anil was filtered, washed with ethanol, and crystallised; yield 70-80%.

Chalkones of 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthaldehyde.—A few drops of 50% NaOH were added to a warm ethanolic solution of the aldehyde (1 *M*) and the appropriate ketone (1.1 *M*) under shaking. The mixture was left for 7 days at room temperature (30°) and then acidified with acetic acid. The separated product was washed and crystallised; yield 40-60%.

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